

FROM WASTE TO CIRCULARITY: VITRIMERIZATION IN THERMOSET COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The demand for thermoset composites is growing rapidly, driven by urbanization, expanding infrastructure, the push for lightweight and fuel-efficient vehicles, and the increasing use of wind energy systems. This growth is largely due to the excellent mechanical strength, chemical resistance, and low maintenance requirements of thermoset composites.

However, these materials are difficult to recycle. Their tightly crosslinked, three-dimensional covalent structures make them thermally stable but non-meltable, which severely limits conventional recycling options. Current methods, such as pyrolysis and solvolysis, break down the polymer matrix to recover the reinforcing fibers, but they typically destroy the resin in the process. Fully recycling both the resin and fibers remains a major challenge. As a result, there is a growing push to develop more sustainable, circular approaches to composite recycling, an urgent need for the future of advanced materials.

One promising solution is vitrimer chemistry. Vitrimers belong to a class of materials known as Covalent Adaptable Networks (CANs), which rely on thermally activated exchange reactions. In vitrimers, a dynamic covalent bond is broken only when a new one is formed, keeping the network intact. These bonds become increasingly dynamic at higher temperatures, allowing the material to soften without losing structural integrity. This unique behavior enables vitrimers to be reshaped, self-heal, and even recycled in a closed-loop process, all while maintaining high performance.

In this work, we explore the practical application of vitrimer technology and highlight its potential to address one of the biggest challenges in the field: designing high-performance composites that support a circular economy.

VITRIMER CHEMISTRY IN THERMOSET COMPOSITES

Thermosetting composites are a class of high-performance materials formed by reinforcing a thermosetting polymer matrix with fibers, fillers, or other strengthening agents [1]. Unlike thermoplastics, thermosetting polymers undergo an irreversible curing process, typically initiated by heat, radiation, or chemical additives, resulting in a rigid, crosslinked molecular structure. This crosslinking imparts excellent mechanical strength, chemical resistance, dimensional stability, and thermal performance, making thermosetting composites ideal for demanding structural and functional applications. Common thermosetting resins include epoxy, polyester, vinyl ester, and phenolic systems, which are frequently combined with reinforcing materials such as glass, carbon, or aramid fibers. These composites are widely used in industries ranging from aerospace and automotive to wind turbines, and marine engineering, where lightweight yet durable materials are essential.

Despite their advantages, thermoset composites pose a major challenge: they cannot be reprocessed after curing due to their permanent covalent crosslinking of the matrices. This limits recycling options to mechanical, thermal, or chemical recovery methods (Figure 1), all of which are energy-intensive and often degrade the material quality [2,3].

Figure 1: Traditional methods used to recycle polymer composites. Adapted from ref. [3]

To address this issue, emerging research focuses on Covalent Adaptable Networks (CANs). CANs offer the mechanical strength of thermosets along with the reprocessability and reshaping capabilities of thermoplastics. This is achieved through the incorporation into the networks of covalent bonds, which undergo reversible chemical reactions in response to external stimuli such as heat or UV light. These chemical exchanges allow the polymer network to rearrange, maintaining its overall structure and function while altering the connectivity between chains. As a result, CANs behave like traditional thermosets at low temperatures, but above a certain threshold, the dynamic bond exchange enables chain mobility and flow. Additionally, these reversible bonds allow the material to self-heal by temporarily increasing chain mobility without compromising structural integrity or mechanical properties [4-6].

Typically, bond exchange within CANs occurs through one of two mechanisms [7]: a dissociative mechanism, where crosslinks break apart into reactive fragments before reforming, or an associative mechanism, where a reactive group within the network directly replaces an existing bond through substitution (Figure 2). The associative pathway is central to the function of vitrimers, a newer class of CANs that exhibit dynamic behavior while maintaining network integrity, offering significant advantages for high-performance applications. Introduced by Prof. Leibler in 2011 [8], vitrimers have brought new challenges and misconceptions regarding their design and functionality.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of dissociative and associative bond exchange mechanisms

governing CANs. Adapted from ref. [7]

The term vitrimers originates from their characteristic viscosity–temperature relationship, which parallels that of vitreous silica. These materials exhibit a continuous decrease in viscosity with increasing temperature, following an Arrhenius-type dependence at elevated temperatures. This behavior facilitates dynamic processes such as thermoforming, autonomous self-healing, and closed-loop recyclability through bond exchange reactions, motivating the growing interest in these systems especially in terms of sustainability in different industrial fields, including composites [9,10]. Because of this, there's growing interest in designing and developing thermoset composites using vitrimer technology. Research is now focusing on several key challenges, one of the most important being how fillers affect the movement of polymer chains, known as molecular mobility. Molecular mobility plays a major role in how the material behaves under stress (its viscoelastic properties) and how well it can be reshaped or repaired. While fillers can improve the material's strength and durability, they might also make the polymer chains less flexible. If that happens, the material's ability to rearrange its bonds—which is crucial for self-healing and reprocessing—can be reduced.

Understanding how different fillers interact with the polymer network is therefore essential for developing high-performance, recyclable vitrimer-based composites. Moreover, practical considerations related to manufacturing and scalability must be taken into account. These include the workability of the reactive mixture, its compatibility with existing processing technologies (e.g., molding, extrusion, or hot pressing), and the ability to achieve consistent and reliable performance in the final product. Parameters such as curing conditions, pot life, viscosity, and integration with reinforcement materials must be optimized for large-scale production.

Due to these stringent requirements, the range of thermosetting chemistries suitable for vitrimer formulations is currently limited. Only a few polymer platforms, those that offer a favorable balance between dynamic network behavior, filler compatibility, and processability, are considered viable for real-world applications. This limitation is illustrated in Figure 3, which outlines the most used matrix systems for vitrimer composite development.

Figure 3: Vitrimer chemistry for thermoset composites. Adapted from ref. [11]

In transesterification-based vitrimers (Figure 3a), epoxy reacts to form exchangeable ester linkages bearing a β -hydroxy group. This chemistry allows for tunable exchange kinetics by adjusting the type and amount of catalyst, offering control over activation energy and processing conditions. However, under off-stoichiometric conditions, careful regulation of network formation is required to prevent the

formation of non-dynamic ether linkages, which can create rigid clusters and compromise vitrimer adaptability. Imine-based vitrimers (Figure 3b) offer robust and dynamic bond exchange via free-amine or imine metathesis, with high bond stability and minimal side reactions. Their advantages include simple synthesis, tunable properties, and excellent mechanical performance, though careful water management is required during formation to prevent internal defects that may be detrimental. Vinylogous urethane-based vitrimers (Figure 3c) enable catalyst-free dynamic exchange via Michael addition or iminium intermediates, offering fast relaxation times and good stability comparable to epoxy/acid systems. Advantages include hydrolysis resistance, water-compatible synthesis, and tunable exchange through external catalysts. However, challenges include managing water release during formation and ensuring long-term stability of free amines to prevent oxidative degradation. Disulfide-based vitrimers (Figure 3d) offer catalyst-free exchange via a [2+1] radical-mediated mechanism at moderate temperatures, making them easy to implement with accessible precursors and widely used in formulations like epoxy and rubber. However, their dynamic properties can degrade over time due to thiol oxidation in air and the thermal sensitivity of the S–S bond. Transcarbamylation (Figure 3e) enables dynamic exchange in both aliphatic and aromatic polyurethanes, with aromatic structures allowing catalyst-free reactions between phenols and urethanes. Siloxane bonds, known for their high chemical and thermal stability, are common in materials like silicone rubber and glass (Figure 3f), making them attractive for dynamic materials. While traditional silyl ethers exchange slowly, recent advances using a base catalyst have enabled much faster siloxane bond exchanges, offering promising applications in composites with readily available commercial precursors. Carbon nanotubes, graphene, glass fibers or inorganic powders, such as silica (SiO_2) or alumina (Al_2O_3) are used as reinforcement fillers for vitrimeric composites [11,12].

A growing body of literature highlights the versatility of vitrimeric composites, demonstrating their applicability across diverse technological domains. In particular, they have emerged as promising candidates in the field of smart electronics, where their dynamic properties can be leveraged for advanced functionality. In their work, N.J. Van Zee et al. [13] developed conductive thermoset composites by dispersing less than 10 wt.% multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) into a polyimine-based vitrimer, obtained by thermally curing terephthalaldehyde, diethylenetriamine, and tris(2-aminoethyl)amine. These composites combined dynamic covalent bond exchange with the electrical conductivity and mechanical reinforcement of MWCNTs. Remarkably, they maintained stable conductivity after multiple deformation and healing cycles, making them potential candidates for recyclable flexible electronics.

Figure 4: Polyimine-MWCNTs vitrimer composites for flexible electronics. Adapted from ref. [13]

Glass fibre-reinforced vitrimer composites have been developed using both epoxy and vinylogous urethane matrices. Prepreg sheets prepared and consolidated via hot pressing or resin transfer molding (RTM) resulted in dense multilayer composites with improved mechanical properties. Despite high fibre

volume fractions (>50 vol%), these composites retained weldability through dynamic covalent chemistries such as transesterification and amine exchange, enabling adhesive-free joining. The mechanical performance matched that of conventional glass fibre/epoxy systems, highlighting the potential of vitrimer-based prepregs for structural applications, particularly in aerospace where large or complex geometries are required.

An alternative approach is based on the conversion of permanently cured systems into exchangeable thermoset composites. This is achieved by mechanically grinding the cured resin, then treating it with a dynamic exchange catalyst and reinforcing filler under elevated temperature and pressure. The resulting material is a fully crosslinked composite that retains structural integrity while offering improved thermomechanical performance and the ability to undergo thermal reprocessing.

In their work, A. R. de Luzuriaga and his colleagues optimized a fabrication method for fibre-reinforced vitrimer composites involving hot-pressing woven carbon fibres with vitrimer powders derived from mechanically ground, cured DGEBA-based matrices [14]. The formation of the composite material occurred through exchange transesterification reactions within the hot-pressed powder, using a one-minute dry process, faster than conventional liquid-state thermoset processing. The resulting composites retained thermoformability and reprocessability, expanding their manufacturing potential and highlighting the importance of vitrimer particle size in promoting effective healing and full recovery of mechanical properties.

A notable study explored the vitrimerization of thermoset polymers using hydroxyl-rich cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) as fillers for the fabrication of vitrimeric epoxy-based nanocomposites [15]. The process relied on the use of planetary ball milling to grind the crosslinked resin and mix it with CNCs (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Catalyst-free vitrimerization based on transesterification of a thermoset resin into a vitrimeric composite through the use of planetary ball milling technique. Adapted from ref. [15]

Interestingly, the abundant hydroxyl groups on CNCs facilitate dynamic transesterification at the polymer interface, initiating mechanochemical activation and network reconfiguration thus effectively converting the rigid, irreversible network into a vitrimer composite structure. The authors demonstrated that incorporating CNCs as a source of external hydroxyl groups significantly enhanced the rate of exchange reactions and improved the thermomechanical performance of the resulting epoxy vitrimer. Beyond improving recyclability, the bio-based CNCs also contributed to mechanical self-healing and enhanced material recovery. This method offers a sustainable route for upcycling both thermoset and lignocellulosic wastes into functional vitrimer materials, making it a promising strategy for scalable, industrial applications.

In this work, a case study on the development of vitrimeric composites by modifying epoxy resins with cellulosic fibers is also discussed. The study aims at generating reliable and reproducible data on

the reprocessability of epoxy-based thermosetting resins and at elucidating the influence of key experimental parameters on both material performance and process optimization. The study begins with the preparation of a well-defined epoxy/anhydride system, which is thermally cured to form a crosslinked network representative of conventional thermoset matrices. To simulate an end-of-life treatment scenario, the cured resin is subsequently subjected to ball milling, a mechanochemical technique that reduces the material to fine powder without the use of solvents, in line with sustainable processing approaches.

The milled resin powder is then combined with a predetermined amount of hydroxyl-rich natural fibers, selected for their ability to promote dynamic transesterification reactions due to the presence of –OH functional groups. The reprocessability of the resulting formulations is systematically investigated by varying processing parameters, namely temperature, pressure, and time, during hot pressing. These parameters are chosen based on their relevance to vitrimeric bond exchange kinetics and their practical applicability in scalable manufacturing settings.

An initial qualitative assessment is conducted by evaluating the morphological homogeneity and structural integrity of the reprocessed specimens. Subsequently, a quantitative evaluation is performed by determining a global mechanical quality index, which serves as a comprehensive indicator of the physical performance and cohesion of the vitrimeric composites post-reprocessing.

This methodology aims to establish a robust experimental framework for the assessment of post-consumer thermoset waste treatment and its conversion into reprocessable composite systems. The findings are expected to contribute to the broader effort of integrating circular economy principles into the lifecycle of high-performance polymeric materials by enabling the recovery and reuse of crosslinked thermosets and reinforcing fibers.

The overarching goal of this work is to explore and validate the feasibility of producing recyclable thermoset materials with high added value. By combining renewable feedstocks with dynamic covalent chemistry and environmentally friendly processing, the activity contributes to advancing sustainable practices in the field of polymer science and composite materials. Ultimately, it aims to broaden the scope of circular strategies for thermosets, integrating waste valorization and recyclability into the design of advanced functional materials.

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